

Progressing the ‘Safe and Sustainable by Design’ Framework for Greener Enzyme-based Innovations

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Key Messages:

- Prioritization of hazard assessment in SSbD excludes OXIPRO’s enzyme-based solutions despite their environmental impact potential creating a major gap in the evaluation of substances that could contribute significantly to European sustainability goals.
- The SSbD assessment of OXIPRO’s enzyme-based innovations faced challenges typical of early-stage innovations, where risk and exposure data are scarce or limited, and assessment methods are not yet well-developed.
- Addressing these barriers requires fostering collaboration and SSbD training, refining methods for early-stage assessments, and alignment of policies.

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Purpose:

This policy brief presents recommendations derived from the experience in using the SSbD framework in the context of four enzyme-based innovation cases in the Horizon Europe funded OXIPRO project¹, as policy input for future refinement of the framework.

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The urgency for transitioning to safer and more sustainable chemical solutions

Chemicals are crucial for societal function and economic performance, yet they contribute to climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss² and threaten human health. A 2024 survey found that 84% of the over 26,000 respondents expressed concern about the effects of harmful chemicals in everyday products on their health³, with an equal proportion also worried about their impact on the environment. This underpins the need for more proactive risk assessment before marketing chemicals.

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000607>; <https://www.oxipro.eu/>

² United Nations Environment Programme, International Science Council. *Navigating New Horizons: A global foresight report on planetary health and human wellbeing*. Nairobi, 2022

³ European Commission. *Attitudes of Europeans towards the Environment*. Special Eurobarometer 550, 2024

The Chemical Strategy for Sustainability represents a major shift in EU's chemical policies, strengthening existing regulations (like REACH) while introducing new approaches to innovation and risk management to promote safer and more sustainable chemicals, and at the same time reducing harmful substances in the environment. Alongside this, new regulations for sustainable product design and manufacture are emerging, including the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR).

In 2022, the initial criteria⁴ and EC recommendation⁵ for establishing the 'safe and sustainable by design' (SSbD) framework, along with methodological guidance⁶ was published. The framework has undergone two testing phases involving stakeholder consultations in case studies and workshops, and is currently being integrated under the Horizon Europe framework program.

SSbD is currently a voluntary approach to guide the innovation process for chemicals and materials from early stages of innovation and along their entire life cycle. The SSbD approach consists of two phases: a design phase and an assessment phase, which are applied iteratively as data become available. The design phase applies guiding principles to shape development, while the assessment phase involves hazard identification, worker exposure during production, exposure during use, and life cycle assessment. The SSbD framework can help steer innovation towards green and sustainable chemistry, going beyond current regulatory compliance and in alignment with European consumer needs and expectations.

Enzymes are catalysts offering environment-friendly solutions

Enzymes speed up chemical reactions in living organisms and are used in many industries to create greener solutions. Enzymes, regardless of the catalytic activities, are characterized as Type 1 respiratory sensitizers⁷, which has recently been categorized as substances of concern (SoC) in the ESPR⁸. When exposure is controlled and limited, experience demonstrates that enzymes can be used safely⁹.

⁴ Caldeira, Carla, et al. *Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials. Framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2022.

⁵ European Commission. Commission Recommendation (EU) 2022/2510 of 8 December 2022 establishing a European assessment framework for "safe and sustainable by design" chemicals and materials. In *Official Journal of the European Union* (Vol. 325, 179–194). European Union.

⁶ European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Abbate, E., et al., *Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials - Methodological Guidance*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2024

⁷ Martel, Cyril, et al. "Bibliographic review on the potential of microorganisms, microbial products and enzymes to induce respiratory sensitization." *EFSA Supporting Publications* 7.9 (2010): 75E.

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 of the European Parliament and of The Council of 13 June 2024 establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for sustainable products, amending Directive (EU) 2020/1828 and Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 and repealing Directive 2009/125/EC.

⁹ EuropaBio - The Essential Role of Enzymes - The unintended impact of the REACH revision on Enzymes and consequences for EU Green Deal Objectives. (2022, September 12). ENP Newswire.

SSbD assessment of enzyme-based innovations in the OXIPRO project

The OXIPRO project focuses specifically on a type of enzymes called oxidoreductases that help transfer electrons between molecules in chemical reactions. A scoping analysis was used to define the goal and scope of OXIPRO’s four oxidoreductase-based innovation cases: sunscreens, detergents, home textiles, and nutraceuticals. The design principle for energy efficiency (SSbD3) was identified in the detergent and textile cases, while nutraceuticals and textile cases shared principles such as material efficiency (SSbD1) and use of renewable sources (SSbD4). Sunscreen case was founded on the principle to prevent hazardous emissions (SSbD5) into the marine ecosystem (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Goal, scope, system boundaries and design principles identified in the four OXIPRO innovation cases.

Challenges to implementing the SSbD approach in OXIPRO and recommendations

In the following table, we summarize the challenges encountered in assessing the safety and sustainability of OXIPRO's enzyme-based innovation cases using the SSbD framework. Based on our experience, we provide recommendations for future refinements of the framework.

Implementation aspect	Challenges	Recommendations
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritization of hazard assessment exclude enzymes despite their proven safety and environmental benefits. Inconsistent SSbD integration during the R&D and innovation process. • Unclear trade-offs between safety, sustainability, and socio-economic factors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote standards and guidelines for SSbD implementation. • Promote a comprehensive non-hierarchical approach balancing safety and sustainability. • Create a multi-criteria decision support system for early-stage innovations.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited data and inefficient sharing hinder early-stage hazard and sustainability (LCA) assessment of chemicals. • Lack of methods for early-stage safety and sustainability evaluation. • Lack of standards and clear guidelines for socio-economic assessment (LCC and S-LCA), leading to a bias on sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support regulatory use of new approach methodologies (NAMs) and computational modelling, including AI, for data generation. • Promote the SSbD toolbox testing phase for purpose alignment. • Support standardized life cycle evaluations and improve early-stage assessment by developing methods for scaling lab data to industrial levels.
Knowledge and skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring consistency and objectivity in the critical assessments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate SSbD training customised for researchers, stakeholders and value chains. • Support an educational platform, with tools, methods and guides.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Covering safety and sustainability through the entire life cycle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate knowledge transfer for tiered SSbD assessment throughout the life cycle.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costly and time-demanding data gathering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop guidance for a tiered assessment • Create incentives to increase demand for SSbD products. • Allocate funding for R&D of SSbD implementation.
Regulatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear alignment of the SSbD with policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve policy coherence, harmonize safety and sustainability policies, including definitions, methodologies, and criteria.

 Conclusions:

OXIPRO's four innovation cases align with key SSbD principles and show the potential of enzyme-based solutions to reduce environmental impacts. However, safety and sustainability assessments at early stages of the innovation process faced challenges due to data gaps, methodological shortcomings, and regulatory uncertainties. Addressing these barriers requires fostering collaboration and training, refining methods for early-stage assessments, and aligning policies.

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